

PREDICTION OF CREEP PROPERTIES OF NICKEL-BASE SUPERALLOY SINGLE-CRYSTAL SRR99

A. M. Hashem

Assistant Professor, Prod. Engg. and Design Dept.,
Faculty of Engg. and Tech., Minia University,
Minia, Egypt.

Abstract

As the most of the high temperature Nickel-base alloys, the high creep resistance of SRR99 is achieved by the precipitation of the intermetallic phase Ni_3Al , which is known γ' phase.

Constant load creep curves has been obtained at temperature from 850 to 950 °C for the SRR99. By analysis of data recorded in tests having a maximum duration of only about 1000 hours, the creep and creep fracture properties for fracture life in excess of 200,000 hours (almost 25 years) can be predicted successfully by using the Θ Projection Concept. This method will be focused initially on the prediction of the long-term data, which it needed for design of components and structure operating at elevated temperature.

This study is shown that by using this approach long-term data creep rupture may be predicted from short term experiments.

Keywords

Creep properties, prediction, nickel-base superalloy single-crystal (SRR99), Θ Projection Concept, creep life, short-term data and long-term data.

1. Introduction

High temperature components which used in power generation, petrochemical, aerospace and atomic energy applications were normally designed to avoid failure within a specified design life. In the pressure vessels and pipe work industry several design codes has evolved to enable safe component design to be effected using simple, conservative techniques. Where components are operating in the creep regime these techniques usually relate the complex stress state in the component to the uniaxial creep data for the relevant material [1].

The nickel-base superalloy single-crystal (SRR99) is selected for the study. The creep behaviour of single crystals shows serious differences from the behaviour of polycrystalline alloys. The material is highly anisotropic and its application at much higher temperatures causes several difficulties specially those concerning with the thermal stability of the micro-structure (known gamma prime, γ' , phase) [2,3].

Long-term creep tests are expensive and sometimes almost

impossible to be performed accurately. Thus the creep life prediction by extrapolating short-term creep data to long-term is vital importance.

Various techniques of creep life predictions such as the Larson-Miller [4], Sherby-Dorn [5], Manson-Hafered [6] and Monkman-Grant [7] methods has been proposed so far. However, it is widely accepted that creep life prediction was limited up to three times the longest tests duration available [8].

Brown, Evans and Wilshire [9] have proposed a new creep life prediction method (Θ Projection Concept method) which was based on the creep time law containing four parameters, Θ_i ($i=1$ to 4). Once the stress and temperature dependence of Θ was determined at high stresses and temperatures, it is in principle possible to predict the entire creep curve at lower stresses and temperatures. They applied the new method to a $\frac{1}{2}$ Cr $\frac{1}{2}$ Mo $\frac{1}{4}$ V steel and demonstrated that it can predict the minimum creep rates after 30 years from the creep data within 3 months.

The new technique is quite interesting because it can predict the whole characteristics of creep data under low stress levels and describe accurately the full creep curve behaviour which the designers need. The extrapolation potential of the Θ parameters has been evaluated by comparison of the predictions with data for constant load uniaxial tension test. However, only a few reports [8-11] is available to confirm the applicability of the new method.

The purpose of the present study is to examine the validity of this assumption. An analysis has been made of data obtained for nickel-base superalloy single-crystal (SRR99), whose data are available in the literature [12].

2. Creep Time Law

A candidate technique for the improvement of data extrapolation and subsequent in scatter band for long term data is the Θ Projection technique [1,9]. This is a recently developed approach to creep curve modelling which is rapidly gaining recognition for its success in extrapolating the results of short term uniaxial specimen tests to service life times. The evolution of creep strain (ϵ) with time is expressed as :

$$\epsilon_c = \epsilon_t - \epsilon_0 = \underbrace{\Theta_1 [1 - \exp(-\Theta_2 t)]}_{\text{primary component}} + \underbrace{\Theta_3 [\exp(\Theta_4 t) - 1]}_{\text{tertiary component}} \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_0 is the initial strain on loading and ϵ_t is the total strain at time, t . The parameters Θ_1 and Θ_3 then quantify the extents of the primary and tertiary stages with respect to strain while the rate constants Θ_2 and Θ_4 define the curvatures of the primary and tertiary stages respectively [14]. The parameters Θ_i ($i=1$ to 4) are depending on temperature and stress.

The first term of the right of Equation (1) is to represent the effect of work hardening usually dominant in primary creep and the second term is to describe the acceleration of creep which becomes apparent in the tertiary stage of creep. The differentiation of Equation (1) leads to Equations (2) and (3)

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \Theta_1 \Theta_2 [1 - \exp(-\Theta_2 t)] + \Theta_3 \Theta_4 [\exp(\Theta_4 t) - 1] \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \epsilon}{\partial t^2} = -\Theta_1 \Theta_2^2 \exp(-\Theta_2 t) + \Theta_3 \Theta_4^2 \exp(\Theta_4 t) \quad (3)$$

From eq. (3), the time to a minimum creep, t_{\min} is given by eq. (4)

$$t_{\min} = [1/(\Theta_2 + \Theta_4)] \ln(\Theta_1 \Theta_2^2 / \Theta_3 \Theta_4^2) \quad (4)$$

It is clear that Equation (1) cannot express steady state creep rate. However, it appears generally to age-hardened creep resistant alloys because the steady state creep is usually short if present and sometimes totally absent [8].

3. Materials and Creep Data Sources

Creep data on a nickel-base superalloy single-crystal, SRR99, in the literature [12] were used in this study. The testing temperatures are 850 and 950 °C and a range of stresses are 200 to 650 MPa, in step of 50 MPa. The fraction value of the γ' -phase is 60% approximately. The chemical composition of the alloy in wt.% is listed in Table 1.

After solution heat-treated at 1305 °C for 2 hours, specimens were cooled in the air and were subjected to an thermomechanical treatment, which consisted of 20 hours at 1000 °C and 100 MPa using a constant tensile creep machine. Specimens for this heat treatment had longitudinal axis within 10 degree of [001] to change the γ' -phase from cubic shape to rafting shape. The rafting was perpendicular to the tensile stress direction. This heat treatment is chosen because there is no incubation time, which is follow the primary stage and defined as the time during strain remains constant with increasing time. Details were documented by Hashem [12].

Table 1 Chemical composition of SRR99

Al	Co	Cr	Ta	Ti	W	C	Ni
5.5	5.0	8.5	2.8	2.2	9.5	0.015	bal.

In fact, Equation (1) was proposed to describe creep curves under a constant stress, however, it may be applicable to constant load creep in tension tests.

4. Results of Analysis and Discussion

4.1 Creep Curve

The comparison between calculated creep curves are shown in Figure 1 at two temperatures 850 and 950 °C and different level of stresses together with the actual strain read from the enlarged creep curves.

It is seen that Equation (1) can express the creep curves satisfactorily except the early stage of primary creep and a last portion of the tertiary creep, specially at low stresses, corresponding to the advent of neck formation. At low stresses the primary creep and tertiary stages of creep were not accuracy. In such a case, the parameters related to the shape of primary creep, Θ_1 and Θ_2 are rather hard to be determined. However, even in such a case the creep curve is represented well by Equation (1).

4.2 Θ -Projection Analysis

An important feature of the Θ Projection Concept is that in addition describing the shapes of individual creep curves through Equation (1), each Θ parameter varies systematically with stress and temperature as evident from the data in Figures 2 and 3. In this way, the Θ analysis provides a quantitative description of the

changes in creep curve shape with changing test conditions. In fact, the variation of each Θ parameter with stress (σ) and temperature (T) can be conveniently described by using the equation

$$\ln \Theta_i = a_i + b_i \sigma + c_i T + d_i \sigma T \quad (5)$$

where a_i, b_i, c_i and d_i are constants (with $i=1,2,3,4$), which are listed in Table 2.

Fig. 1 Comparison between experimental and calculation creep curves at different level of stresses and two test temperatures a) 850 °C & b) 950 °C.

Fig. 2 Variation of Θ_i parameters vs. engineering stress at temperature 850 °C.

Fig. 3 Variation of θ_i parameters vs. engineering stress at temperature 950 °C.

Table 2 Values of the coefficient in Equation (5)
(Units are second, degree K and MPa)

θ_i	a_i	b_i	c_i	d_i
θ_1	-2.813	0.005	0.002	-4.2×10^{-6}
θ_2	1.033	-0.009	-0.001	8.0×10^{-6}
θ_3	0.007	-4.6×10^{-5}	-6.1×10^{-6}	4.1×10^{-8}
θ_4	-2.739	0.003	0.002	-1.8×10^{-6}

These values, together with Equations (1) and (2), allow creep curves to be constructed for any stress and temperature within the experimental ranges covered but, with this procedure, the point of fracture at any test condition is not defined. However, the fracture life for any stress and temperature can be satisfactorily specified as the time to reach the failure strain or creep ductility, ϵ_t . For this reason, information is required to define the dependence of the creep ductility on stress and temperature.

4.3 Stress Dependence

The criterion discussed in the previous section was employed in the range of stresses 200 to 650 MPa and temperatures 850 and 950 °C are shown in Figures 2 and 3. The results of the regression analysis are given as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \log \Theta_1 &= -2.1 + 1.34 \cdot 10^{-3} (\sigma / \text{MPa}) \\
 \log \Theta_2 &= -4.53 + 5.0 \cdot 10^{-3} (\sigma / \text{MPa}) \\
 \log \Theta_3 &= -5.2 + 1.48 \cdot 10^{-3} (\sigma / \text{MPa}) \\
 \log \Theta_4 &= -4.1 + 4.86 \cdot 10^{-3} (\sigma / \text{MPa}) \\
 \log \Theta_1 &= -2.15 + 1.69 \cdot 10^{-3} (\sigma / \text{MPa}) \\
 \log \Theta_2 &= -2.93 + 6.0 \cdot 10^{-3} (\sigma / \text{MPa}) \\
 \log \Theta_3 &= -5.93 + 6.38 \cdot 10^{-3} (\sigma / \text{MPa}) \\
 \log \Theta_4 &= -2.97 + 6.7 \cdot 10^{-3} (\sigma / \text{MPa})
 \end{aligned}
 \quad \begin{array}{l}
 850 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \\
 \\
 \\
 \\
 950 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \\
 \\
 \\
 \end{array}
 \quad (6)$$

As Evans et al. [9] and Li et al. [8] has already shown in the study, the variation of the logarithm of Θ parameters is well represented by a linear relationship. This is quite convenient for both interpolation and extrapolation.

4.4 Time Dependence

4.4.1 Time to a Minimum Creep

The relation between time to a minimum creep t_{\min} and stress is shown in Figure 4 on a double logarithmic scale, where solid circles designate of the experimental results of the time to a minimum creep reported by Hashem [12]. While the solid line signify the time at a minimum creep determined from Equation (3). The experimental and prediction values of time to a minimum creep and time to fracture for two test temperatures 850 and 950 °C and different level of stresses are listed in Table 3.

4.4.2 Time to Fracture

Usually, the fracture time, t_f is long enough to allow the reduction of Equation (1) to Equations (7) and (8) because the values of both $\exp(-\Theta_2)$ and Θ_3 are very small.

$$\epsilon_f = \Theta_1 + \Theta_3 \exp(\Theta_4 t_f) \quad (7)$$

or

$$t_f = \text{Ln}[(\epsilon_f - \Theta_1) / \Theta_3] / \Theta_4 = P, \quad (8)$$

where ϵ_f is the fracture strain and P is the life prediction parameter. The fracture time is plotted against P in Figure 5. In the present case, the fracture strains are between 0.14 to 0.195 at temperature 850 °C, while these values are between 0.24 to 0.34 at temperature 950 °C. It is seen that the linearity between P and t_f is excellent compared with the calibrating line which is the slope equal to 45°. The comparison of the experimental and prediction time to fracture values are given in Table 3.

Fig. 4 Time to a minimum creep for experimental and calculation data vs. engineering stress at two test temperatures a) 850 °C & b) 950 °C.

Fig. 5 Time to fracture vs. life prediction. a) 850 °C & b) 950 °C.

Table 3 Values of the experimental and prediction values of time to a minimum creep and time to fracture for different temperatures and stresses.

Temp. [°C]	Stress [MPa]	Experimental		Prediction	
		t_{min}	t_f	t_{min}	$t_{f=P}$
850	650	15.5	66.1	15.0	66.2
	600	20.0	94.5	19.5	96.9
	550	31.5	155.8	31.4	159.2
	500	55.0	274.6	50.4	268.7
	450	170.0	826.4	164.1	809.5
950	400	3.7	11.0	3.4	11.8
	350	13.2	32.2	12.9	37.0
	300	21.5	53.6	21.0	59.0
	250	61.5	193.2	61.0	196.3
	200	150.1	419.2	149.2	419.9

The linearity of the relationships in Figures 2 and 3 suggest that the Θ Projection Concept can be used again for extrapolation and for interpolation of creep properties, as previously for a wide range of polycrystalline materials [8,9]. However, in the present case, actual long-term stress-fracture properties were available in order to allow an assessment to be made of the behaviour patterns predicted using the Θ technology [11]. Specifically, the fracture life was determined as the time to reach the failure strain for any stress and temperature using Equation (7). Clearly, the predicted curves are well within the ranges observed experimentally. Since the long-term creep rupture properties are predicted accurately, it would therefore seem reasonable to conclude that the creep strain and creep rate data which can be derived easily from the Θ relationships [8] can also be used in design calculations for this alloy.

5. Conclusion

In the light of the previous results and discussions, it is possible to draw the following conclusions from this study:

1. The Θ Projection Concept is considered an accurate prediction of the fracture time and evolution of creep strain with time.
2. Analysis of high precision creep curves obtained for nickel-base superalloy single-crystal. SRR99 shows that, over wide ranges of stress and temperature, the variation of the creep strain with time, time to a minimum creep and time to fracture can be described accurately by using the Equations (1,4,8)

$$\epsilon_c = \epsilon_t - \epsilon_0 = \Theta_1 [1 - \exp(-\Theta_2 t)] + \Theta_3 [\exp(\Theta_4 t) - 1]$$

$$t_{\min} = [1 / (\Theta_2 + \Theta_4) \ln(\Theta_1 \Theta_2^2 / \Theta_3 \Theta_4^2)]$$

$$t_f = P = \ln[(\epsilon_f - \Theta_1) / \Theta_3] / \Theta_4$$

References

- [1] Taylor N.G., Twaddle P.R., and Hurst R.C., Proceedings of Fourth Inter. Con. held in Swansea, 1990, pp. 985-998.
- [2] Doller M., and Bernstein I.M., Superalloy 1988, Proceedings of Sixth Inter. Symp. on Superalloys, Pennsylvania, 1988, pp. 275-284.
- [3] Nathal M.V. and Ebert L.J., Metall. Trans., Vol. 16A, 1985, pp. 1863-1870.
- [4] Larson F.R. and Miller J., Trans. ASME, 1952, pp. 74-756.
- [5] Sherby O.D., Dorn J. A., and Orr R.L., Trans. ASM, 1945, pp. 46-113.
- [6] Whittenberger J.D., Metals Handbook Ninth Edition, Vol. 8, ASM, 1985.
- [7] Sundararajan G., Mat. Sci. Engg., A112, 1989, pp. 205-214.
- [8] Li G., Sakai T., and Endo T., Proceedings of the Third Inter. Conf. held in Swansea, 1987, pp. 803-813.
- [9] Brown S.G.R., Evans R.W., and Wilshire B., Scripta Metall., Vol. 20, 1986, pp. 855-860.
- [10] Shen G., and Plumtree A., Proceedings of the Fourth Inter. Conf. held in Swansea, 1990, pp. 999-1008.
- [11] Evans R.W., Fadlalla A.A., Wilshire B., Proceedings of the Fourth Inter. Conf. held in Swansea, 1990, pp. 1009-1016.
- [12] Hashem A.M., Ph. D. Thesis, Minia Univ., Minia, Egypt, 1991.